

THE UNIQUENESS OF INTERNATIONAL PIRLS RESEARCH IN THE FORMATION OF CREATIVE SKILLS

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Abstract. *In this article, the experiments carried out in the field of education by the developed countries of the world are also carried out in the schools of our country as an example. In Uzbekistan, all conditions have been created for the young generation to receive quality education. In particular, PISA, PIRLS, TIMSS researches can be used as examples.*

Keywords: *globalization, developing society, international studies, PISA, PIRLS, TIMSS studies, Zealand education, assessment process, educational development, leadership of the Russian Federation.*

We live in a globalizing era, in a developing society. We are facing drastic changes in every field. Currently, the demands placed on society members are very high. It is imperative and necessary that changes and innovations in every aspect of our society meet world standards. In particular, the requirements for the education sector, for the education of students, and the delivery of quality knowledge to them are very high. It is important for our students to receive education in accordance with world standards, to provide education to students based on international experiences and for the leader of our country became one of the requirements. The head of our state Sh.M.Mirziyoyev named this year "Year of attention to people and quality education" for no reason.

Currently, all conditions have been created for the young generation to receive quality education in our peaceful and peaceful Uzbekistan. Experiences implemented in the field of education by the developed countries of the world are being implemented in the schools of our country as an example. Examples include PISA, PIRLS, and TIMSS studies.

Young people studying in general educational institutions of the Republic of Uzbekistan will participate in international research from 2021. The decision of the Cabinet of Ministers dated December 8, 2018 No. 997 "On measures to organize international research in the field of education quality assessment in the public education system" was adopted. [3]. Based on it, the participation of 9th grade students in PISA, primary school students in PIRLS, 4-th and 8-th grade students in TIMSS and the tasks to be performed in this regard were determined.

Since the evaluation process is an important criterion for determining the progress of education, the first steps were taken to implement international programs for evaluating the knowledge of general secondary school students at the initiative of the Ministry of Public Education. In this regard, the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated September 5, 2018 No. PF-5538 "On additional measures to improve the public education management system" [2]. and Decree No. PF-5712 "On approval of the concept of development of public education of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030", [4].

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PIRLS (Progress in International Reading Literacy Study) is an initial is an international assessment system that assesses the quality of reading and comprehension levels of students studying in the classroom. This test type is every 5 years is intended to be held for the first time, and according to the results of its latest research in 2016, the Russian Federation is leading. The International Association for the Evaluation of Educational Achievement is an international partnership of national research institutes, research agencies, scholars, and analysts working to evaluate, understand, and improve education around the world. More than 60 countries and more than 100 educational institutions participate in this network of non-profit and independent organizations. Since 1958, the IEA has taken measures to eliminate deficiencies in the educational system in the process of assessing students' literacy in mathematics, natural sciences, and reading potential. It differs from other international organizations by creating activities and acceptable recommendations.

The initiative of Uzbekistan's participation in the research of the PIRLS program for 2021 was welcomed by the IEA organization and it was noted that the organization will provide all necessary support and recommendations.

In addition, organizational issues related to participation in PIRLS-2021 research, i.e. conditions of participation, stages of research implementation, guidelines for effective organization of research and many other tasks were discussed in detail at the meeting. As part of the PIRLS research, the quality of reading and the level of understanding of the read text of the 4-th graders of countries with different educational systems are studied. The choice of 4-th grade students for these studies is important because it is precisely in the fourth year of study that students have a high level of learning, to form their ability to acquire knowledge in further education, and thus to modern times. helps in successful adaptation.

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In most countries, children start school at the age of 6. But in England and New Zealand, education starts at the age of 5. Therefore, students from the 5-th grade, not the 4-th grade, will participate in the project.

The age of the students whose reading and text comprehension quality is checked is 10.5 years. Since children in Eastern countries start studying at the age of 7, 10.7-10.9-year-old students take part in the research. PIRLS research is coordinated by the International Association of Educational Institutions (IEA). The PIRLS project is considered a leader among international studies on determining the level of development of reading ability of primary school students. PIRLS studies have been conducted at the level of primary education for 5 years since 2001. It has a high place among international studies. The number of countries participating in this program is

increasing every year. It has been held 4 times since 2001. The last PIRLS research was conducted in 2016. So far, 35 to 50 countries have participated.

The goals and objectives of the PIRLS International Survey, the procedure for conducting the PIRLS Educational Testing Service (USA), Statistics Canada (Canada), the Data Processing Center of the International Association for the Assessment of Educational Achievement (Germany) and Boston College the world's leading scientific centers such as the International Center (USA) are participating) The participation of these organizations in the development of pedagogical measures for evaluating the educational achievements of schoolchildren based on experimentally tested international standards is the organization of PIRLS research and allows to ensure high quality of transmission. The purpose of the PIRLS study is to compare reading comprehension levels of fourth-grade students from different countries around the world, as well as to identify differences in reading literacy across national education systems.

According to the international dictionary of research, "reader literacy" is the ability of a person to understand and logically understand the various written languages necessary to fully express himself in life and achieve his goals.

PIRLS research is aimed at solving the following problems: - development of objective measures and tools reflecting world priorities in the field of education; - comparative assessment of the effectiveness of the organization of the country's educational process; - identification of contextual factors that influenced the research results; - having evidence-based information recognized by the international community. The object of the study is the educational achievements of primary school graduates, because it collects all the knowledge and skills of teaching in the fourth academic year.

At this age, students should be well versed in reading so that they can use a variety of texts in structure and format to continue successfully in mainstream school.

Description of research tools.

International PIRLS research tools include:

- Notebook with texts and questions.

Student questionnaire.

- Teacher's information.
- Parents form.

Form of school administration.

- National handbook of observers.

Regional coordinating manual.

A guide for the school coordinator.

- Study guide.
- A guide to job evaluation and response coding.

Formation of creative thinking and creative imagination in students PIRLS is required of students in the international program. Among them, A. Ismailov, D. Norboeva and others. Methodical manual "Evaluation of reading literacy of primary school students in PIRLS international studies" [7.45] shows the mechanisms of formation and evaluation of these skills. In order for students to understand the essence of their personal creative activities, it is necessary to conduct current and final reflection exercises. For example, creative assignments based on the text "On the Road" by Shukur Kholmirezayev from the current 3rd grade textbook:

From the 3-rd grade reading book "YOLDA" Shukur Kholmirezayev [8.39].

Father, mother and son were coming to the city.
Mother and father - a child on a horse in the donkey.
Field road. The day has warmed up. The child is thirsty. He asked his father for water.
- Hold on, my son, hold on. There is a spring on the way down to the town. You drink from that.

We drink too. "We will also water the fields," said his father.
The boy persevered and drove the donkey.
The air is hotter than hot. On the dirt road, the Allanimas were creaking.
Tandir is like an oven that has come out of itself. The child's thirst for water is worse it was hard. His palate hardened and his lips began to stick together. Crying sent He asked for water.
- There is no water, my son. You see it yourself. So you have to be patient.

An impatient person cannot withstand difficulties. "I'm resilient!" that think "Distract yourself, look around," advised his father.

They continued on their way. Flowing under the stones on the way down to the city they reached the spring. They got off the slopes.

Everyone was happy. They also drank water from the spring.
They also watered their crops. Then they slowly set off.
- What now, my son! Will it be possible? - said his father
- Yes, as long as one can bear it. Does he distract himself, does he do something else, it's still bearable.

Patience is the best thing in a person explained that it is one of the qualities.

Task 1: Why was the son thirsty?

Task 2: Explain the words using the "Analysis of Concepts" method.

"Analysis of concepts" method.

Content of the concept

Spring

Choose

Ulov

Now

Endurance

Difficulty

Virtue

Task 3: Write "Sinquain" to the following words based on the topic.

Mother, father, son.

Example:

1. Mother

2. Caring, kind

3. Raises, caresses, hugs

4. A mother brings up her child with care.

5. Mother

1. Mother

2. _____

3. _____
4. _____
5. _____

1. Father

2. _____
3. _____
4. _____
5. _____

1. Son

2. _____
3. _____
4. _____
5. _____

Task 4: What rivers are there in Uzbekistan?

Task 5: Write a short story on the theme "Save the island".

Save the island

Task 6: Tell about parents from proverbs.

1. _____
2. _____
3. _____

Similar reflection questions form students' creative thinking and creative imagination.

For the effective formation of creative activity, it is necessary to first instill creativity and creativity in students, and then this activity should find its expression in the products they create.

Observations and experiences of advanced pedagogues show that students' creative activity does not develop adequately during primary education. Formation of creative activity in students directly depends on biological and social pedagogical factors.

The formation of creative abilities is accelerated in 7-10-year-old students. Creative activity in this period will have a certain limit. A solid memory and a desire to create in students is the basis for the formation of creative abilities.

In conclusion of the above-mentioned points, it should be said that the formation of creative abilities of elementary school students should become one of the main goals of the direct educational process. The process of formation of creative abilities in elementary school students is organized as specific educational situations and embodies the mechanisms of student personality development.

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